

THE RESULTS OF THE STUDY ON THE TECHNICAL CONDITION OF HYDRAULIC STRUCTURES IN RESERVOIRS

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Summary: *The article discusses the results of a study on the technical condition of hydraulic structures in reservoirs that have been in operation for a long time. During this operation, various long-term effects of use, design, construction, and operational issues of reservoirs were observed, as well as factors affecting the reliability of their hydraulic systems. The article presents main criteria for ensuring reliable operation of these systems.*

Keywords: *reservoir, hydraulic structures, operation, dam, filter, pump station, malfunction.*

INTRODUCTION.

The age of hydraulic structures in the country varies from 50 to 60 years or more, and their technical condition has deteriorated due to long-term use. This has resulted in a decrease in their operational capacity and reliability, as well as lack of maintenance. Furthermore, the lack of consideration for environmental factors during construction and operation has contributed to the decline of these structures' reliability.

In order to provide the economy of Uzbekistan with water resources, there are 59 water reservoirs that are currently being exploited, of which 29 are in channel and 30 are off-river. As a rule, existing flood reservoirs are also used as reservoirs. Their restoration is carried out with the help of special self-propelled channels or a machine-lifting device from water sources for the purpose of replenishing the natural reserves of the regions with water. The total water volume of all water bodies exceeds 20,0 km³, of which 1 billion.m³ more than 5 units, 0,5 to 1 billion.m³ up to 4 units, from 100 to 500 million.m³ up to 15 units, from 10 to 100 million.m³ up to 17 units, 10 million.it consists of less than 18 water bodies per m³ [1-4].

Of the used water jets, 22 of them have been exploited since 15 to 25 years, 26 of them from 25 to 35 years, 11 of them more than 60 years. Of the 59 water bodies being exploited, 22 are classified objects [5-6].

The significance of this issue stems from the fact that, despite considerable progress in the operation of hydraulic structures, a rising rate of failures in these systems has been observed in recent years. These incidents have resulted in incidents at reservoirs, pumping stations, and rivers, causing increased costs for repairing the structures annually.

To address this challenge, changes need to be made regarding the safety of hydraulic structures. This includes constant monitoring and timely processing of data from monitoring and measuring devices installed in reservoirs. It is also essential to analyze compliance with inspection regulations and evaluate structural strength using

innovative techniques. Furthermore, experience from other countries in this field should be taken into account. A skilled approach to evaluating the safety of existing structures is crucial for ensuring their continued safe operation [2,3].

RESEARCH METHOD.

The scientifically based results of this research will allow us to develop effective practical measures to ensure the reliability of hydraulic structures and prevent possible emergencies [4]. In order to ensure that any safety issues with reservoir facilities do not occur or their impact is minimized, it is necessary to identify the causes of these issues and develop measures to prevent them using a separate approach.

To assess the reliability of reservoir hydraulic structures under the influence of various factors, the technical condition of several reservoirs has been studied. One of the main problems in reservoir operation is overfilling, which can lead to the washing of reservoir banks under the influence of waves and the filling of the reservoir with mud [5].

The probability of an accident in water bodies increases when the Earth shakes during floods and in other emergency situations. Due to the daily use of hydraulic facilities and various impacts over the course of their permanent use, factors influencing their reliability arise. In order to ensure the reliable operation of these water bodies, certain fundamental criteria need to be met. [3,6-9]:

- at the beginning of this year, a structured dispatch plan was implemented, taking into account changing conditions throughout the year. This ensured reliable water supply to all consumers.

- control the growth of shores, the turbidity of water entering the basin and the application of counter-measures to reduce the useful volume of water in the range of years, while reducing the turbidity rate of the basin;

- high slope of the dam in increasing the reliability of the exploitation of reservoirs prevent such cases as violations of the protective elements, disturbance of the plates in the atmosphere effect (air temperature and humidity change, wind), rupture, silage, absorption;

- in the filtration processes of dams and their foundations, a significant amount of water is wasted from the dams (along with groundwater). Over time, the dams on the soil structure of the dam become larger, as do the cavities that appear. This is due to increased water consumption through seepage, migration of soil layers, and washing out.

RESEARCH RESULTS.

As a research object, the Talimarjan Water Reservoir, located in the Nishan district of the Kashkadarya region, was selected. The district, where the reservoir is located, has a seismicity of 7 points. The building's capital class is II, and construction

was completed between 1974 and 1983. The reservoir was put into operation in 1985. It has a total water volume of 1,525 million cubic meters and a usable volume of 1.4 billion rubles. The dam is of the same type, with a height of 35 meters and 2 additional heights of 36 meters. The water discharging plant is a type 2 turbine, and the permeability of water in the center of the dam is 360 cubic meters per second (Figure 1).

a) reservoir bowl

b) upstream slope position

Fig. 1. Talimarjan water reservoir

According to the results of the study, the technical condition of the reservoir hydraulic structures revealed the following:

1. The top of Dam-1 is in a satisfactory condition, but there have been some issues detected at the 390-meter mark on the berm that supports the dam. Specifically, there are deformations in some of the slabs (P23-P60), as well as in the slope plates that are attached to the berm. Additionally, some of the reinforced concrete slabs that make up the cladding for the dam are showing signs of slipperiness and exposed deformation seams.

At this point, there is also a 6-8 meter per second rate of filtration into a collector through a reinforced concrete pipe that carries sediment. Due to wind, sand is collecting in this pipe, possibly coming from the rainwater drainage system through a rainwater intake well. However, the water intake pipe does not have a reverse filter to prevent soil spillage from occurring. As a result of this, water is leaking from the slope areas of P46-70, causing soil to flow down the slope and into the collector, creating pressure build-up.

2. In the case of a water level above the 392 meter mark on the lower slope, the rise of filtration water was observed.

3. Closed tubular drainage on the right bank of the drain cannot withstand a decrease in the depression curve when the water level is above 392 m, as water is leaking from the wells of № 7 piezometer at P4 ÷ 35 and № 6 and № 7 piezometer at P5 ÷ 70.

To observe the vertical and horizontal movements of the dam, fundamental

dams, planned elevation marks, concrete and soil surface marks, and depth marks are installed. Hydraulic triangulation points are also installed to measure water level changes.

In dam 1, 234 piezometers are monitored, but 7 are not working and 10 have insufficient water level control when there is none.

In dam 2, only 27 were used, with 6 being periodically dry. Thus, 35 piezometers need cleaning in dam 1. For 7, 76 meters need replacing, and for 6, 67 more will need digging.

Their sensitivity is low and unsatisfactory due to drilling the wells with a muddy solution and pressing the piezometer filters muddy. It is necessary to check them once a year to increase accuracy. In the reservoir, this work has never been done.

According to data from the Bathymetric Center, the useful capacity of the reservoir as a result of turbidity is 58 million. m³.

The physical and mechanical characteristics of the soil on the body and ground of the dam have not been studied since the period of operation.

The average sinking rates of the elevation marks on the top of the Talimarjan reservoir dam 1 are given in table 1.

Table 1

Average immersion speed of height marks above the dam

Field picket	Date	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
	upstream level, m	393,9	383,0	397,5	382,0	393,5	393,9	394,8	396,9
P-14-29	V _s , mm/y	-4,94	-2,60	-5,64	-2,11	-5,49	-2,31	-8,62	-4,25
P 30-45	V _s , mm/y	-13,26	-1,67	-8,84	-2,56	-6,48	-1,34	-7,53	-3,88
P 46-61	V _s , mm/y	-8,44	-2,17	-6,02	-2,72	-5,31	-1,71	-8,36	-3,35
P 64-80	V _s , mm/y	-7,87	-3,26	-6,39	-2,70	-5,79	-2,35	-9,09	-3,52
P 82-98	V _s , mm/y	-	-2,69	-2,63	-2,83	-6,11	-2,62	-7,76	-3,52

CONCLUSION.

If we compare the rates of deposit of dam stamps in this table, it seems that the water level in the dam is correlated with the water levels between 2011 and 2018. In 2019, some of these construction works were carried out by company employees at a slower pace, while in 2020, these works accelerated.

In summary, in order to ensure that each factor does not have a significant impact on the results of the analysis, it is necessary to identify the origins of its occurrences based on a separate scientific examination of each of them and take measures to

eliminate these sources.

Determining the safety criteria of hydraulic structures and assessing the risk of accident of hydraulic structures, as well as the study of defects that cause complete or partial loss of capacity of the facility and studying the defects and exploring several options to ensure their sustainability is a difficult engineering task.

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